

A large, hairy tarantula spider is the central focus, positioned on a piece of weathered, light-brown wood. The spider's body is dark brown and covered in fine, light-colored hairs. Its legs are thick and also covered in hair. To the left of the spider, a delicate white spider web is visible, partially covering the wood. The background is a soft, out-of-focus blue-grey color.

THE EUAGRIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Euagridae has a worldwide distribution and is represented by 12 genera and 81 species. The genera *Allothele* Tucker, 1920 and *Euagrus* Ausserer, 1875 represented by five species are known from South Africa. The species of *Allothele* have a wide distribution and are listed as Least Concern. The status of the single species *Euagrus atropurpureus* Purcell, 1903 remains obscure and maybe misplaced.

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FAMILY EUAGRIDAE Raven 1979

The family Euagridae has a worldwide distribution and is represented by 12 genera and 81 species. From South Africa two genera and five species are known (Word Spider Catalog 2020). The genera were transferred from Dipluridae to Euagridae by Opatova et al. (2020).

COMMON NAMES: Euagridae Sheet-Web Spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 16–22 mm, males more slender and slightly smaller than females. Colour varies from orange-brown, purple-brown, dark grey or blackish brown. Carapace hairy; cephalic region low and thoracic region elevated; eight eyes in compact group on eye tubercle; chelicerae projecting anteriorly; rastellum absent; endites without cuspules; sternum longer than wide. Abdomen oval; hairy; posterior spinnerets long and tapering; terminal segment not pseudo segmented; median spinnerets short and widely spaced. Legs slender; scopulae absent; tarsi long and slender; leg I of males usually with mating spurs on the tibiae and metatarsi. Cymbium of male palp bi-lobed and spinose.

LIFESTYLE: The Euagridae are ground dwellers, and construct their sheet-webs with a funnel retreat close to the soil surface. The web consists of a flat, slightly concave, non-adhesive silk sheet (40–60 cm wide) laid over the ground or any horizontal surface. The sheet is composed of a mesh of silken threads suspended by oblique and vertical threads. The funnel retreats usually extend under rocks and logs, but may also be built in abandoned animal burrows. The web usually remains in the same place and is repaired and enlarged as the spider grows. Males abandon their webs and search for mates during the wet summer months (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002; 2014).

TAXONOMY: The *Allothele* genus was revised by Coyle (1984). *Euagrus* (only one sp.) recorded from South Africa but possibly misplaced.

Dorsal and ventral view of *Allothele teretis* from Opathe NR Photo ASD

Eye pattern Photo ASD

GENUS *ALLOTHELE* Tucker, 1920

Allothele comprises a distinctive group of Euagridae spiders living in southern Africa. The African genus is represented by five species of which four are known from South Africa (Word Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Allothele Sheet-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Allothele caffer* (Pocock, 1902)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size 8–12 mm. Colour medium to dark brown, carapace with radiating stripes. Carapace with dense hair cover consisting of thin recumbent setae; eyes in compact quadrangle, wider than long; fovea a deep transverse groove, usually recurved, with two erect setae side-by-side in front of fovea; sigilla small, round and subequal in size; endites and labium lack cuspules; cheliceral furrow with 9–14 medium-sized to large teeth on pro-margin and 6–50 along proximal one-third on retrolateral side. Abdomen oval; hairy; median spinnerets short; unsegmented with distinct hirsute sclerite just anterior to base; posterior spinnerets longer than carapace with terminal segment longer than basal or middle segment. Leg III usually longer than I or II; males with a well-developed non-terminal mating apophysis on tibia II with stout tooth-like apical and subapical spines. Palpal bulb of male simple, pyriform with elongated, ridged embolus; females with setae-lined spermathecae.

LIFESTYLE: Very little is known about the behaviour and ecology of *Allothele* species. They seem to be adapted to savanna and forest habitats with dry winters and rainy summer seasons. They make sheet-webs with funnel-retreats partly (or wholly) sheltered in subterranean cavities, under rocks, in rotten logs, in leaf litter or under bark. The males abandon their webs in search of mates during the wet summer months. *Allothele teretis* typically builds a sheet curtain-web in cool, shady places such as on tree trunks and in or across holes on stream.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Coyle (1984).

Allothele malawi female Photo Peter Webb

Allothele sp. retreat Photo Liz Herholdt

Allothele australis (Purcell, 1903)

COMMON NAME: Eastern Cape's Sheet-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described Purcell (1902) as *Thelechoris australis* from Dunbrody in the Eastern Cape. Presently known from two provinces (EOO= 56 580 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 37-1652 m a.s.l.) and five protected areas. Although threatened by loss of habitat for urbanization and farming activities in part of its range the species still occupies a wide geographical range and the overall population has not yet decline significantly, therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Lives in sheet-web with a funnel retreat, located beneath stones and in rock crevices. Sampled from the Fynbos, Thicket and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Cookhouse (-32.75, 25.817); Grahamstown Botanical Gardens (-33.3, 26.52); Dunbrody, Sundays River (-33.47, 25.55); Grahamstown (Melrose House) (-33.33, 26.54); Line Drift (-33.068, 27.205); Mpofu Nature Reserve (-32.606, 26.597); Peddie (-33.196, 27.116); Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.185, 26.502); Fairy Vale (-33.19, 26.37). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Somerset West (-34.081, 18.840).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve; Mpofu Nature Reserve; Tsolwana Nature Reserve and Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005). The species is threatened by loss of habitat for infrastructure development around Peddie, Grahamstown and Somerset West and crop farming in Cookhouse.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Coyle (1984). Known from both sexes.

Allothele australis female from Addo NP Photo Linda Wiese

Left palp, after Coyle (1984)

Spermathecae, dorsal view after Coyle (1984)

Allothele caffer (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Allothele Sheet-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1902) as *Euagrus caffer* from Durban in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is recorded from three provinces, including two protected area (EOO= 20 833 km²; AOO= 28 km²; 17-1316 m a.s.l.) and is suspected to still be under sampled especially in the Eastern Cape. Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes a sheet-web with a funnel retreat. It was sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Indwe, Lady Frere (-31.47, 27.35). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Durban (Bluff) (-29.86, 31.05); Durban (Burman Bush) (-29.85, 31.01); Umhlali (Chakas Rock) (-29.47, 31.22); Umhlanga Lagoon Nature Reserve (-29.7, 31.09); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.16, 30.37).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the following areas: Umhlanga Lagoon Nature Reserve and Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Coyle (1984) and known from both sexes.

Allothele caffer female Photo Les Oates

Left tibia and metatarsus II, prolateral view after Coyle (1984)

Left palp, after Coyle (1984)

Left tibia II, after Coyle (1984)

Spermathecae, dorsal view after Coyle (1984)

Allothele malawi Coyle, 1984

COMMON NAME: Malawi Sheet-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Coyle (1984) from Malawi. In South Africa, the species is recorded from three provinces including two protected area (EOO= 63 064 km²; AOO=36 km²; 520-1519 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes a sheet-webs with a funnel retreat. *Allothele malawi* was sampled from Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Malawi and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria, Waverley (introduced) (-25.778, 28.253). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lake Fundudzi (-22.86, 30.29); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Mukumbani Ivory Route (-22.88, 30.4); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Kruger National Park, Punda Malia (-22.68, 31.01); New Agatha Forest (-24.03, 30.08). **Mpumalanga:** Sabie (Lone Creek Falls) (-25.1, 30.78).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in three areas such as Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019; Muelelwa et al. 2010); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and New Agatha Forest. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Coyle, 1984).

Allothele malawi female from Waverley Photo Peter Webb

Left tibia and metatarsus II,
after Coyle (1984)

Left palp and spermathecae,
dorsal view after Coyle (1984)

Allothele teretis Tucker, 1920

COMMON NAME: Common Allothele Sheet-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1920) from Mfongosi near Ubombo, KwaZulu-Natal. It is known from two protected area (EOO= 68 881 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 223-2019 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They build a curtain-like sheet-web in cool, shady places such as tree trunks and holes on stream banks. The species is sampled from Forest, Grassland and Savanna Biomes (Foord et al. .2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Estcourt (-29.03, 29.85); Estcourt (10 km SE, Griffins Hill) (-29, 29.87); Keate's Drift near Mpofana (-28.85, 30.5); Kranskop (-28.97, 30.86); Tugela River near Middelrift (-32.82, 26.98); Mfongosi near Ubombo (-27.28, 32.15); Mhlopheni Nature Reserve (-28.96, 30.39); Muden (-28.96, 30.39); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52; 31.66); Weenen Nature Reserve (-28.84, 30.07); Winterton (15 km NW Spioenkop Nature Reserve) (-28.81, 29.53); Dundee Mpofana near Dundee (-28.161, 30.222).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for crop farming around Estcourt and Weenen, but vast areas of suitable habitat remain within its range, the overall population is not suspected to be significantly declining. The species is also protected in the Mhlopheni Nature Reserve and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Coyle (1984) and known from both sexes.

Allothele teretis female Photo Charles Haddad

Spermathecae, dorsal view after Coyle (1984)

Left tibia and metatarsus II, after Coyle (1984)

Left palp, after Coyle (1984)

Allothele teretis female Photo ASD

GENUS *EUAGRUS* Ausserer, 1875

The genus *Euagrus* Ausserer, 1875 is represented by 22 species known from Mexico and Taiwan but the one known from South Africa is possibly misplaced (Word Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Sheet-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Euagrus mexicanus* Ausserer, 1875

MORPHOLOGY: Endites without cuspules; sternum longer than wide; cymbium of male palp bilobed and spinose; posterior spinnerets long and tapering but terminal segment not pseudosegmented.

LIFESTYLE: Unknown.

TAXONOMY: The single species recorded from South Africa is possibly misplaced.

Euagrus atropurpureus Purcell, 1903

COMMON NAME: Prince Albert's Sheet-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape Province endemic described by Purcell (1903) from the type locality Prince Albert (EOO<500 km; AOO= 4 km²; 614 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from Nama Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Species possibly misplaced.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from female.

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